

Machine Learning application in predicting the properties of Ti-6Al-4V samples produced with Power Bed Fusion technology

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Abstract

In the context of Additive Manufacturing (AM) with high-cost materials such as Ti-6Al-4V (Ti64), minimizing physical experimentation through predictive models offers a strategic advantage in reducing lead time and manufacturing costs. In view of this, the present study attempts to build a systematic framework to establish such a predictive compacity. In particular, eight supervised Machine Learning (ML) models are compared based on their performance in predicting critical physical properties of AM components, i.e., 3D surface roughness, relative density, and hardness. The curated dataset comprises both traditional dimensional printing parameters and dimensionless parameters. Specifically, in addition to the conventional Volumetric Energy Density (VED) and four primary printing parameters (laser power, hatching distance, scanning speed, and layer height), the study discusses two dimensionless numbers Π_1 and Π_2 for property prediction. This work underscores the role of selecting predictors and models in advancing data-driven process optimization, offering a scalable approach for reducing experimental overhead in metal AM.

Keywords: Powder Bed Fusion, surface roughness, relative density, hardness, Machine learning, process-structure-property, Ti64

1 Introduction

Recent years have witnessed the growth in applying Additive Manufacturing (AM) technology in producing hard-to-machine Ti-6Al-4V (Ti64) alloy [1, 2]. It is an alloy valued in aerospace and defense for its high strength-to-weight ratio, corrosion resistance, and thermal stability [3, 4]. Yet these properties also complicate traditional manufacturing methods [5, 6], making advanced techniques like Powder Bed Fusion (PBF) an essential alternative for processing [7]. The technology works on powder as stock materials and employs a laser source that can fuse (sinter or melt) powder particles together to fabricate a 3D object, which can have highly complex geometry [8]. Beyond titanium, PBF is also applied for printing various metals [9, 10], including stainless steel, maraging steel, aluminum, Inconel, etc. The technology allows for the fabrication of highly complex designs with density approaching those of casted components, making it a valuable tool in modern industries.

In metal printing with PBF technology, adjusting the printing process parameters can govern multiple complex physical phenomena that occur due to the rapid powder - liquid - solid transitions [11, 12]. This includes the absorption and reflection of the laser power, heat conduction, heat radiation, fluid flow, material emission, vaporization, and chemical reactions [13, 14]. In the existing literature, process parameters can be classified into four categories being the machine setup, laser setup, scanning procedure, and material properties [14]. The improper choice of process parameters can lead to the problems of lack of fusion, keyhole formation, gas porosity, crack, delamination, balling, and significant residual stress [15, 16]. Different parameters such as laser power, scanning speed, hatch distance, scanning strategy, layer height, part orientation are among the most commonly studied process parameters [17–19]. For instance, increasing the laser power enlarges the melt pool, promoting better bonding [20]. This, in turn, increases the relative density and reduces residual stress. In addition, a high scanning speed does not allow enough time to fully melt the stock material, resulting in poor bonding and decreased hardness [21]. Similarly, increasing the hatch distance reduces the fusion of nearby powder particles within a single layer, leading to incomplete melting and a lower density in the printed part [22]. Alongside scanning speed and hatch distance, increasing the layer height can accelerate the printing rate. However, thicker layers carry a higher risk of incomplete melting, which can lead to higher surface roughness [23]. Process parameters directly affect the melt pool size, material fusion, and microstructure, thereby influencing the properties of the printed materials [24, 25].

To control the properties of printed metal in general or Ti64 specifically, instead of focusing on single process parameters, other quality metrics such as Energy Density (ED) for linear, area, or volume are derived [26]. These metrics are particularly useful because they correlate many process parameters that are crucial for PBF technology with the output, usually printed properties. For example, Volumetric Energy

Density (VED) accounts for the whole amount of energy input by the PBF system to the print and is calculated with four most impactful process parameters, that is, laser power, scanning speed, hatching distance, and layer height. As reported in [27], for Ti64 printing, the common ranges for laser power is (70 - 100) W , scanning speed is (70 - 1800) mm/s , hatching distance is (50 - 140) μm , and layer height is (20 - 50) μm . From the same paper, the typical ranges for printing Ti64 alloy of existing commercial and self-built machines is between 30 J/mm^3 and 210 J/mm^3 . The dual (α - β) phase of Ti64 is directly affected by the energy or heat input and the rapid heating-cooling cycles of the PBF process. This, in turn, vastly influences the mechanical properties of printed Ti64 and results in a finer microstructure compared to its casted counterpart [28]. A review of the existing literature in [27] reported that the optimal range for relative density is more than 60 J/mm^3 , surface roughness is (61 - 80) J/mm^3 , microhardness is (61 - 70) J/mm^3 , while tensile strength is more than 90 J/mm^3 . It is worth noting that VED may not capture all aspects of the printed properties. For instance, while the density of printed Ti64 products reported in [29] and [30] was similar (both are higher than 99.5%), the VED levels were significantly different (150 J/mm^3 vs. 60 J/mm^3). This discrepancy could be attributed to differences of either the density measuring method or the laser beam diameters. The latter results in variations in laser intensity and melt pool dimensions, which are not accounted for in the VED calculation. In addition, even when a number of samples are printed with the same VED, their final characteristics are influenced by individual parameters, as evidenced by different morphology, porosity, microstructure, and tensile strength of the Ti64 samples in [31–33].

In addition, other so-called dimensionless numbers can be investigated. Dimensional analysis is widely used in aerodynamics and heat transfer applications, but not as common in manufacturing, especially for PBF process. The formulation of dimensionless numbers helps provide a means for comparison across different PBF systems [34]. According to [34], instead of having a formula that directly relate the input process parameters to the output properties, the formulation can be done with dimensional analysis. This reduces the number of process parameters needed for evaluation by combining groups of variables into a non-dimensional form that reflects specific physical phenomena [35]. This approach also highlights which sub-processes are important for further investigation. According to [36], there are four types of non-dimensional variables for PBF process that are the non-dimensional heat input, the Peclet number (Pe), the Marangoni number (Ma), and the Fourier number (Fo). However, over the years, numerous dimensionless numbers have been derived [34, 37–40].

Most of the dimensionless numbers would require the information about the melt pool characteristics that are usually not available for users. For example, although both [35] and [39] derived their dimensionless numbers using the Buckingham Π theorem, the dimensionless numbers in [35] attempt to correlate material porosity solely with process parameters and material properties. In contrast, those in [39] focus on the fabrication of lattice structures, requiring more detailed information about the melt pool. It is worth noting that information about the melt pool can help incorporate important physical phenomena occurring during the PBF process, such as evaporation,

recoil pressure, buoyancy and capillary forces, Plateau-Rayleigh instability, Marangoni convection, and temperature-dependent material properties [41, 42]. The variety of dimensionless numbers in the existing literature arises from different authors attempting to incorporate various process parameters relevant to control and predict specific output properties, in order to cope with the complex nature of the PBF process.

From another perspective, Machine Learning (ML) has been extensively studied by researchers to advance AM in five key areas: Design for Additive Manufacturing (DfAM), material analytics, defect detection and monitoring, process modeling and control, and sustainability [43]. A bibliometric analysis of 10,054 articles published in 20 years up to 2020 across five major databases (ACM, IEEE Xplore, ScienceDirect, SpringerLink, and Scopus) reveals ML's significant contributions to AM, particularly in detection, monitoring, prediction, and process optimization. The study in [43] highlights that quality-related topics dominate this research, with frequent references to keywords such as property, porosity, defect, and monitoring. In general, ML models learn patterns from established datasets to map inputs to outputs, enabling the generation of desired outputs based on new inputs provided by operators. This capability enables real-time decision-making. Moreover, ML models can be continually improved by updating them with new data from ongoing experiences or additional inputs [44]. Through Transfer Learning (TL), the learned knowledge can also be generalized and applied to similar tasks [45]. It is particularly advantageous for AM due to the high costs associated with acquiring data from printing and sample measurements. In recent years, ML has garnered significant attention in the research community as an efficient alternative for processing large AM datasets. Compared to computationally expensive multi-physics and multiscale simulations [46, 47], ML offers more efficient processing and deeper insights into AM processes [48, 49]. However, it should be noted that results from numerical simulations complemented with experiments [50] can serve as a valuable data source to guide ML models for better performance.

Recent studies have applied statistical and ML methods to predict quality metrics in PBF AM. For example, Toprak [51] combined DoE, and ML to predict hardness of AlSi10Mg using 27 samples, where Support Vector Machine (SVM) achieved the highest accuracy ($R^2 = 0.73$). Gor et al. [52] compared Neural Network (NN), K-nearest Neighbor (KNN), SVM, and Linear Regression (LR) as a baseline for SS316L density prediction using multi-source data, with Feed Forward NN (FFNN) reaching $R^2 = 0.95$ but high error, while SVM offered a better balance result of $R^2 = 0.923$. From another perspective, Zhu et al. [53] employed conditional generative adversarial network (GAN) for data augmentation to enhance Vickers hardness prediction of high-entropy alloys, improving DNN performance from $R^2 = 0.71$ to 0.84. In addition, Maitra and Shi [54] predicted 2D surface roughness (R_a) of Ti-6Al-4V using 1211 data points and additional power morphology (Average Particle Size (APS) and Variability in Particle Size (VAR)) parameters, where Gaussian Process Regression (GPR) and NN performed best (Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) of $0.51 \mu m$ and $0.58 \mu m$). La Fé-Perdomo et al. [55] applied Box-Behnken design to establish a dataset for SS316L property prediction with ML models, with Gaussian Process Regression (GPR) best for surface roughness, ensemble model for relative density, and NN for tensile strengths and hardness (all are with accuracy higher than 90%). Later, group of the

same author [56] optimized NN and Adaptive Network-based Fuzzy Inference System (ANFIS) using Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm (NSGA-II) for SS316L surface roughness prediction, achieving $R^2 = 0.984$ and 0.939 , respectively. Benchmarked from AlSi10Mg properties (relative density, surface roughness, and hardness) based on 390 data points, Alamri et al. [57] proved that NN consistently outperformed Support Vector Regression (SVR), Kernel Ridge regression (KRR), Random Forest (RF), and Lasso regression with R^2 up to 0.772 . On a wider scope, Akbari et al. [58] compiled a large dataset (1600 points) across AM metals with various information about the materials and machines to predict the printed properties (strengths, surface roughness, hardness), and demonstrated relatively high accuracy of R^2 minimum 0.85 with RF, Gradient Boosting (GB), and NN. Interestingly, Muhammad et al. [59] used Deep Learning (DL) to predict AlSi10Mg average 3D surface roughness (S_a) from 3D profilometry data measured on 40 round bar specimens, taking into account the location of the samples on the baseplate and measuring locations, with prediction within 5% experimental error. Finally, Toorandaz et al. [60] introduced in-situ S_a prediction using melt pool data obtained from photodiode sensor, where RF and Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGB) outperformed other models in comparison in terms of F1-score.

Inspired by existing literature, this study employs ML to predict the properties of Ti64 components produced using PBF technology. The measured properties include 3D surface roughness, relative density, and macrohardness. Four quality metrics are utilized for the ML studies: the four printing parameters (laser power, scanning speed, hatching distance, and layer height), the VED and two dimensionless numbers. These metrics, along with the measured properties of the components, are used to train ML models and to make predictions. There are two statistical regression models LR, and Ridge Regression (Ridge) employed together with six ML models, that is, SVR, Decision Tree (DT), RF, GB, XGB, and Adaboost (AB), for a better view to the prediction performance. The study aims to evaluate the performance of various ML models in predicting the specified properties. Ultimately, by leveraging the advantages of ML models, this approach seeks to significantly reduce the costs associated with physical testing and computational time.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 1 provides the necessary background to understand the research topic. Section 2 details the materials and methods used in this study, including the process parameters, quality metrics, sample fabrication, property measurements, and the ML models that are employed. Section 3 presents the results of the property evaluation and compares the performance of various ML models in predicting the properties based on the provided data. Finally, Section 4 concludes the paper with an outlook on potential future research directions.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Volumetric Energy Density and dimensionless number

The quality of a product from PBF system depends on several process parameters and their interactions. Thus, it is inadequate to consider each parameter separately while setting up the printing parameters. Rather, it is suggested in the existing literature

to look at the parameters as a whole using a measure such as the VED, which is formulated as follows

$$E = \frac{P}{vht}, \quad (1)$$

where there are the VED E (J/mm^3), the laser power P (W), the scanning speed v (mm/s), the hatching distance h (mm), and the layer height t (mm). It should be remarked that E , which is later interchangeably noted as VED, is a product of four key process parameters in PBF. Given this, two completely different sets of printing parameters can have the same E value as a product. For example, even if both P and v increase twofold, E will remain the same. In general, a higher E input deepens and widens the size of the melt pool, which can result in different microstructure and melt pool [61]. Nevertheless, E has become the most popular metric for evaluating the effect of printing parameters on the properties of PBF-printed products [27].

In addition to the four basic parameters used in Equation (1), more parameters can be taken into account considering the dynamic of the energy distribution within the molten pool. The measure is called a dimensionless number, a scalar used in fluid mechanics and heat transfer studies to describe the thermo-dynamical behaviors of a system [62]. A dimensionless number is presented in [35] as

$$\Pi_1 = \frac{C_p P}{kv^2 h}, \quad (2)$$

where the thermal properties of the material are additionally considered, that is, the specific heat C_p ($J/kg \cdot K$), and the thermal conductivity k ($W/mm \cdot K$). To better understand the physical meaning of Π_1 , we can consider an additional concept of dwell time

$$\tau = \frac{d}{v}, \quad (3)$$

where the dwell time τ (s) is defined as the time the laser beam travels a distance equal to its diameter d (mm). Combining Equation (1), Equation (2) and Equation (3), it is possible to rewrite the dimensionless number Π_1 as

$$\Pi_2 = \frac{C_p}{k} E \tau. \quad (4)$$

From Equation (4), we can observe that the dimensionless number is a function of the material's thermal properties, VED , and the dwell time. The dimensionless number Π_2 is more versatile than Π_1 because it also considers the diameter of the laser beam and the layer height [35]. It should be noted that, as opposed to VED, the dimensionless numbers are unitless. In this study, we utilize these three quality metrics to evaluate the properties of the final product.

2.2 Design of Experiment and sample fabrication

The machine that is used for printing is Renishaw AM400 with the build volume of $250 \times 250 \times 300 \text{ mm}^3$ and the Ti64 powder supply from the same company [63].

Fig. 1: SEM/BSE image of the Ti64 powder in used.

The shape and size of the powder can be observed in Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)/Backscattered Electron (BSE) image in Figure 1.

As can be observed from Figure 1, the Ti64 powder is characterized by spherical particles that is suitable for spreading on the baseplate. From the manufacturer, the composition of the material (% w/w) is Ti (80 - 90)%, Al (6 - 6.5)%, and V (3.8 - 4.5)%.

The printing is done within the inert atmosphere of argon. The printing parameters are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Printing parameters.

Power - P (W)	200; 250; 300
Hatching distance - h (μm)	75; 100; 125
Scanning speed - v (mm/s)	600; 700; 800
Layer height - t (μm)	10; 30; 60
Strategy	Meander

As can be seen in Table 1, each key parameter for calculation of VED in Equation (1) has three values to vary for the calculation of the quality metrics. By combining the parameters, we have printed in total 81 samples for the study. However, for samples with 10 μm layer height, they inherit cracks due to the excessive thermal stress. It should be noted that, in this study, we aim to develop printing parameters as well for practical use. Samples with cracks, thus, are not considered to be successful print. Besides, this hinders the proper measurement of relative density and surface roughness. While the microhardness of the bottom surface can be measured, in order to ensure the uniformity of the study, samples printed in the 10 μm batch are omitted, leaving 54 samples for the study. Their parameters and according quality metrics are listed in Table 2.

Table 2: Configurations of printed parameters and corresponding E , Π_1 , and Π_2 for samples with layer height of 30 μm and 60 μm .

P (W)	h (μm)	v (mm/s)	t (μm)	E (J/mm ³)	Π_1 (-)	Π_2 (-)
200	0.075	600	30	148	598	1096
200	0.075	700	30	127	439	805
200	0.075	800	30	111	336	617
200	0.1	600	30	111	448	822
200	0.1	700	30	95	329	604
200	0.1	800	30	83	252	462
200	0.125	600	30	89	359	658
200	0.125	700	30	76	264	483
200	0.125	800	30	67	202	370
250	0.075	600	30	185	747	1370
250	0.075	700	30	159	549	1007
250	0.075	800	30	139	420	771
250	0.1	600	30	139	561	1028
250	0.1	700	30	119	412	755
250	0.1	800	30	104	315	578
250	0.125	600	30	111	448	822
250	0.125	700	30	95	329	604
250	0.125	800	30	83	252	462
300	0.075	600	30	222	897	1644
300	0.075	700	30	190	659	1208
300	0.075	800	30	167	504	925
300	0.1	600	30	167	673	1233
300	0.1	700	30	143	494	906
300	0.1	800	30	125	378	694
300	0.125	600	30	133	538	987
300	0.125	700	30	114	395	725
300	0.125	800	30	100	303	555
200	0.075	600	60	74	598	548
200	0.075	700	60	63	439	403
200	0.075	800	60	56	336	308
200	0.1	600	60	56	448	411
200	0.1	700	60	48	329	302
200	0.1	800	60	42	252	231
200	0.125	600	60	44	359	329
200	0.125	700	60	38	264	242
200	0.125	800	60	33	202	185
250	0.075	600	60	93	747	685
250	0.075	700	60	79	549	503
250	0.075	800	60	69	420	385
250	0.1	600	60	69	561	514
250	0.1	700	60	60	412	377
250	0.1	800	60	52	315	289
250	0.125	600	60	56	448	411
250	0.125	700	60	48	329	302
250	0.125	800	60	42	252	231
300	0.075	600	60	111	897	822
300	0.075	700	60	95	659	604
300	0.075	800	60	83	504	462
300	0.1	600	60	83	673	617
300	0.1	700	60	71	494	453
300	0.1	800	60	63	378	347
300	0.125	600	60	67	538	493
300	0.125	700	60	57	395	362
300	0.125	800	60	50	303	277

The properties of the printed samples in terms of surface roughness, relative density, and hardness are measured and later subjected to the DoE and ML study. The sample is a prism with 1-mm rounded edges sizing of $10 \times 10 \times 20 \text{ mm}^3$. Their positions on the baseplate are shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2: Distribution of the printed samples on the baseplate.

As shown in Figure 2, we print a total of three builds, each containing 27 samples, making up the 81 samples as planned. Each of the samples is marked with a number for later handling purposes. The separation into three builds is necessary due to the printer's constraint of having only one layer height in one build. Each sample is marked with a number for easier classification. The samples are printed directly on the baseplate and are removed after printing with Wire Electrical Discharge Machining (WEDM) cutting. WEDM leaves the bottom surface sufficient roughness for subsequent hardness test.

2.3 Machine Learning model

In this study, a total of eight models are employed. Two statistical models are LR and Ridge (statistical). Six ML models are SVR, DT, RF, GB, XGB, AB. It should be noted that LR and Ridge assume the linear relationship between the inputs and outputs, which serve as the baseline for performance comparison with other ML models. The ML models are chosen with the consideration that they can handle non-linear and small-sized datasets. Table 3 outlines the ML algorithms that are employed in this study with their corresponding hyperparameters that are tuned for optimal prediction in this study.

Out of the selected models, LR is the simplest regression method. It assumes a linear relationship between independent and dependent variables attempts to fit a straight line to the dataset while minimizing the sum of squared errors. Thus, it cannot capture non-linearity. Ridge extends LR by adding an L2 regularization term to reduce variance and overfitting, making it effective for multi-collinear or high-dimensional datasets, though it still assumes linearity. From another perspectives, SVR applies SVM principles to regression, fitting data within an epsilon margin and can hand both linear and non-linear relationships via kernels such as linear, polynomial, and Radial

Table 3: Select hyperparameter grid configuration

ML algorithm	Hyperparameter grid	Value
RF	random_state	42
	regressor_n_estimators	[50, 100, 200]
	regressor_max_depth	[None, 10, 20]
	regressor_min_samples_split	[2, 5]
	regressor_min_samples_leaf	1
GB	regressor_max_features	'auto'
	random_state	42
	regressor_n_estimators	[50, 100, 200]
	regressor_max_depth	[3, 5, 7]
DT	regressor_learning_rate	[0.01, 0.1, 0.2]
	random_state	42
	regressor_max_depth	[None, 5, 10, 20]
SVR	regressor_min_samples_split	[2, 5, 10]
	regressor_C	[0.1, 1, 10]
	regressor_kernel	['linear', 'rbf']
	regressor_Gamma	'scale'
AB	regressor_decision_function_shape	'ovr'
	random_state	42
	regressor_n_estimators	[50, 100, 200]
	regressor_learning_rate	[0.01, 0.1, 1.0]
XGB	regressor_max_depth	[1, 3]
	random_state	42
	regressor_eval_metric	'mae'
	regressor_n_estimators	[50, 100, 200]
	regressor_max_depth	[3, 6, 9]
	regressor_learning_rate	[0.01, 0.1, 0.3]

Basis Function (RBF). It can perform well on small to medium datasets but being computationally expensive and sensitive to parameter tuning.

Regarding the tree-based models, DT is a non-linear one that split data hierarchically based on feature values, capturing complex relationships but prone to overfitting when too deep. RF mitigates this by combining multiple DTs in parallel (bagging), improving robustness and handling large datasets well, though at a higher computational cost. In contrary, GB builds DTs sequentially, with each DT correcting previous errors. This can achieve higher accuracy for complex patterns but with a cost of more computation and careful tuning than RF. In addition, XGB optimizes GB by adding L1 and L2 regularization, parallelization, and efficient handling of missing values. It can deliver top performance, however, with high model complexity and tuning effort. Finally, AB also combines weak learners (typically shallow DTs). It assigns higher weights on misclassified instances in each iteration so that these difficult cases can be focused on next iteration. However, it remains sensitive to noise and outliers.

The four predictors that are used for predicting the three aforementioned physical properties are: 1) VED , 2) Π_1 , 3) Π_2 , and 4) four printing parameters (P , v , h , t) that comprise the VED (denoted as 4 pars). Tuning of hyper-parameters is realized for all the models and the only the versions with highest accuracy are reported.

The performance of the ML models is evaluated and compared using three key metrics: R-squared (R^2), Mean Absolute Percentage Error ($MAPE$), and Mean Absolute Error (MAE). The first is referred to as coefficient of determination, and the later two are referred to as error metrics.

For regression problems, it is crucial to evaluate the proportion of variance in the dependent variable that can be explained by the independent variables, or R^2 . This metric is calculated as one minus the ratio of the sum of squares of residuals to the total sum of squares. A higher R^2 value indicates better model performance in terms of prediction accuracy. Upon evaluation of R^2 value, it is necessary to note that it can be negative, positive, and even very close to 1. Negative value means that the model predicts worse than the mean value of the target. Positive means that a % of the predicted data can be explained by the input data. In general, higher R^2 value stands for better prediction. However, too high R^2 , for example, R^2 of 1 would imply that there is an over-fitting problem.

Therefore, R^2 cannot be solely used as a quality metric. It is necessary to evaluate R^2 as well with $MAPE$ and MAE . $MAPE$ measures the absolute percentage error by dividing the difference between the predicted and experimental values by the experimental value. On the other hand, MAE calculates the arithmetic mean of the absolute errors between the predicted and experimental values across N data points. It is relatively intuitive because it gives the same unit as the input data. Compared to MAE , $MAPE$ is particularly useful for comparing model performance because it expresses the error as a percentage, making it scale-independent. Nevertheless, it is sensitive to data that are close or equal to 0. For both MAE and $MAPE$, lower values indicate better predictions.

2.4 Property measurements

In this study, we conduct three different tests to characterize the properties of the printed samples including: 3D surface roughness S_a (arithmetical mean height), relative density, and HV30 hardness. There equipment and methodology used are:

- Roughness: 3D roughness measurements were evaluated using optical microscope Alicona InfiniteFocus 5G (IF MeasureSuite, Alicona ImagingGmbH, Raaba/Graz, Austria). We follow standards ČSN EN ISO 25,178 -2/-3 for 3D roughness measurements.
- Density: density measurement was conducted with classic double weighing method or Archimedes method. Specifically, each sample was measured five times in air and five times in distilled water. The density of the samples were then calculated. The evaluation follows ISO 3369 standard.
- Hardness: Macrohardness tests were conducted on the bottom surface of the samples, which were previously cut with WEDM method. Vicker HV30 test following ISO 6507-1:2023 standard was conducted 5 times on each sample with the dwell time of 20s. The hardness measurements were conducted with Universal hardness tester HPO 250.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Fabrication of the samples

As aforementioned, in contrast to the normal printing of samples with layer height of $30\ \mu m$ and $60\ \mu m$, samples with the smallest layer height of $10\ \mu m$ inhibit cracking on their surface. This is because the energy input is too high for such a low layer height, allowing it to excessively penetrate the preceding layers beneath, causing high thermal gradients and leading to cracking. Therefore, for this study, we only evaluate the samples with layer height of $30\ \mu m$ and $60\ \mu m$. The distribution of E , Π_1 , and Π_2 of the samples are depicted in Figure 3.

Fig. 3: The values of three quality metrics (E , Π_1 , and Π_2) calculated for samples with layer height of $30\ \mu m$ and $60\ \mu m$.

As reported in Figure 3 and Table 3, considering both the $30\ \mu m$ and $60\ \mu m$ layer height, E is within the range of $[33; 222]$ (J/mm^3), while Π_1 is $[202; 897]$ (-), and Π_2 is $[185; 1644]$ (-). According to Equation 1, the lower the layer height, the higher the energy input. This is evident from the higher VED level of $30\ \mu m$ samples in comparison with $60\ \mu m$. It is also explainable in practice where laser with the same power setting has to travel twice the distance to achieve the same layer height.

For samples with layer height of $10\ \mu m$, the E , Π_1 , and Π_2 are respectively in the range of $[200; 667]$ (J/mm^3), $[202; 897]$ (-), and $[1110; 4933]$ (-). VED and Π_2 levels of the $10\ \mu m$ are in the range that are significantly higher than the samples printed with greater layer height. In addition, since Equation 2 does not consider the layer height, there is an coincidence of the calculated Π_1 values with the previous two. Besides, despite some overlaps in the range of the metrics E and Π_2 , all the samples in the $10\ \mu m$ batch exhibit cracking, rendering them unsuitable for the study. As a result, they are excluded from the analysis. This emphasizes the dominant role of layer height in printing success, as not only the total energy input but also the dwell time for each layer, which is directly influenced by the layer height, is significant.

3.2 Physical property measurements

The results of the physical measurements in terms of 3D surface roughness, relative density, and hardness are reported together with their quality metrics in Figure 4. From top to bottom, there are three rows reporting E , Π_1 , and Π_2 , respectively. In addition, all the plots of each quality metric show a similar trend. It is noteworthy that even though the calculation of Π_1 and Π_2 scales up E to significantly higher values, they do not have any physical meaning because they are dimensionless.

Fig. 4: The 3D surface roughness, relative density, and hardness of the samples plotted versus their three corresponding quality metrics. The maximum and minimum values are bolded and underlined.

As can be observed from Figure 4, the distributions of the 3D surface roughness exhibits a decreasing trend as E increases. The average S_a is calculated to be 18 μm , with a significant number of samples clustering near this average value. Additionally, the relative density displays a clear exponential increase with rising E . Notably, the

majority of the printed samples achieve a relative density of approximately 99%, highlighting the high quality of the printing process. The distribution of relative density as well aligns with the pattern reported in [35]. Last but not least, the hardness reaches both its maximum and minimum values at relatively low E of around $50 J/mm^3$, highlighting that only VED may not be a good measure for hardness prediction. As the VED continues to increase, the range of variation narrows and eventually converges to approximately $520 HV30$ as E reaches its highest value.

In Table 4, we select only the samples with the lowest or highest measures for the reporting purposes. It should be noted that the samples are assigned with ID numbers that are different from the marking numbers printed on them for better elaboration of the results, which can be assessed together with Figure 5.

Table 4: Selected results of physical properties.

ID	P (W)	h (μm)	v (mm/s)	t (μm)	E (J/mm^3)	Π_1 (-)	Π_2 (-)	Sa (μm)	Rel. density (%)	Hardness (HV30)
1	200	0.1	600	60	56	448	411	7.2	99.4	441
2	250	0.1	700	60	60	412	377	10.1	99.6	531
3	250	0.1	800	60	52	315	289	20.3	99.1	556
4	200	0.125	800	60	33	202	185	21.5	94.4	475
5	200	0.125	700	30	76	264	483	26.3	98.9	537

Fig. 5: The 3D surface roughness Sa of the samples from the side view ranging from lowest to highest: 1) $7.21 \mu m$, 2) $10.1 \mu m$, 3) $20.3 \mu m$, 4) $21.5 \mu m$, and 5) $26.3 \mu m$.

From Figure 5 and Table 4, we can observe that the worst S_a value is from sample 5, which has lower layer height of $30 \mu m$, while the best S_a value is from sample 1, which has higher layer height of $60 \mu m$. This contradicts the typical understanding that lower layer height provides finer layer resolution, reduces the staircase effect, and thereby lowers the surface roughness. This discrepancy could be attributed to the fact that we are experimenting with different combinations of process parameters, where the selected combination may be suboptimal. Such a parameter combination might result in excessive energy density in these thin layers, leading to spatter formation and increased surface roughness. Additionally, thinner layers may cause the melt pool behavior to become more sensitive to laser scanning parameters, further contributing to rougher surfaces. The use of thinner layers also requires more passes of the recoater, which could disturb the powder bed. This effect may also be influenced by the position of the samples on the baseplate [64]. When spreading a thin layer near the argon gas flow source, the layer can become thinner, leading to uneven spreading and resulting in surface irregularities.

In Figure 5, from left to right, it can be observed that samples with lower roughness are characterized by fewer but larger spatters, while samples with higher roughness exhibit the opposite pattern. This suggests that the combination of process parameters used for lower roughness samples is optimal for achieving proper melting of the powder. Assessing together with Figure 4, it can be seen that samples with layer height of $30 \mu m$ in general has higher E and higher S_a . Due to the complex interactions among the process parameters, we may not account for all the necessary process parameters with the introduced quality metrics. Consequently, it is difficult to simply explain the relationship between the process parameters and the output properties using linear relationships. This complexity highlights the potential for using ML methods later on for the properties prediction.

3.3 Machine Learning training and performance comparison

The heatmaps showing the model performance are reported in Figure 8, Figure 9, and Figure 10. It should be noted that the models are evaluated with different splitting of training/testing data starting with 10% training data up to 90% training data with 10%-increment. This is to examine their robustness to variations in training/testing data distributions. The models with the highest performance according to the R^2 , $MAPE$, MAE metrics are summarized in Table 5, Table 6, and Table 7. For better reporting purposes, the names of the ML models and their corresponding % of training-testing data split will be written with their abbreviations and two numbers in brackets. For example, AB (80-20) stands for Adaboost model with training-testing data split of respectively 80% and 20%. The performance of the models are evaluated mainly with R^2 with a threshold values of 0.3. This serves as the criteria for hyperparameter tuning. The reason for R^2 to be prioritized is because it is useful to assess whether the models can explain the general pattern of the dataset well. The $MAPE$ and MAE are additional indicators to show the errors or prediction in % and unit of the predicted values.

Regarding the prediction of 3D surface roughness S_a , Table 5 reports the models with the best performance selected from the heatmap in Figure 8. It should be noted

Table 5: The optimal ML model for predicting the roughness S_a with their corresponding metrics.

	<i>VED</i> AB (80-20)	Π_1 XGB (80-20)	Π_2 RF (80-20)	<i>4 pars</i> SVR (80-20)
R^2	0.13	0.47	0.47	0.02
MAPE (%)	25.16	21.87	18.67	27.38
MAE	3.76	3.09	3.2	3.79

Table 6: The optimal ML model for predicting the relative density with their corresponding metrics.

	<i>VED</i> AB (80-20)	Π_1 XGB (80-20)	Π_2 GB (50-50)	<i>4 pars</i> RF (70-30)
R^2	0.55	0.21	0.14	0.56
MAPE (%)	0.12	0.22	0.25	0.2
MAE	(0)	(0)	(0)	(0)

Table 7: The optimal ML model for predicting the hardness with their corresponding metrics.

	<i>VED</i> SVR (60-40)	Π_1 SVR (60-40)	Π_2 SVR (60-40)	<i>4 pars</i> XGB (80-20)
R^2	0.01	(0)	0.01	0.41
MAPE (%)	2.67	2.66	2.66	1.79
MAE	13.65	13.59	13.61	9.11

that even though R^2 is selected as primary indicator for the model performance, it is not necessary that the performance of the model with highest R^2 is the best. For example, when predicting S_a with Π_1 , GB (90-10) results in a very high R^2 of 0.53. However, its performance is much worse when the training ratio is 10% less. Indeed, GB (80-20) only exhibits R^2 of -0.25, indicating that the model predicts worse than the mean of the target output. This may be dedicated to the underfitting problems. In this manner, XGB is chosen because of its consistent positive R^2 values, that is, (90-10) of 0.52, (80-20) of 0.47, and (70-30) of 0.23. From Table 5, it can be drawn that for predicting the S_a values, the most effective models are XGB (80-20) with Π_1 , and RF (80-20) with Π_2 .

Similarly, for predicting the relative density, see Table 6, the best models are AB (80-20) with *VED*, and RF (70-30) with *4 pars*. It should be noted that the *MAPE* and *MAE* results are remarkably low. To understand this, it is noteworthy to emphasize that the relative density input into ML models for training purposes are smaller than

1. The target variable (relative density) varies within a very narrow range of (0.979 - 0.996), except for an outlier at 0.944 (see distribution in Figure 4, where the values are multiplied with 100 and assigned % for better presentation). For such a scenario with low variance, even a prediction that is slightly off the true values can result in considerably low $MAPE$ and MAE , since the magnitude of the absolute errors are small. $MAPE$ and MAE could not fully reflect the model performance for this scenario. Therefore, they have to be accompanied by the R^2 metric that better reflects the true data patterns.

Finally, for hardness prediction, XGB (80-20) performs the best for 4 *pars*. The results of this study are in agreement with [65] that only nonlinear ML models, i.e., XGB, RF, AB and SVR can perform well with such a highly nonlinear dataset as depicted in Figure 4. Regarding the prediction accuracy, for each predicted property, there is at least one ML model that can yield the R^2 value of more than 0.4, which is as well the baseline for prediction in paper [65].

The parity plots that show performance of the ML models are presented in more details in Figure 6. They correspond to the best models summarized in Table 8, Table 9, and Table 10. In general, it can be observed that all of the selected models achieve satisfactory performance, with minimal observed error. Parity plots of the relative density prediction inherit more tightly clustered data points, which is in agreement with the low variance shown by the low $MAPE$ and MAE measures. On the other hand, parity plots of roughness S_a and hardness prediction show more balanced and scattered datapoints to the two sides of the reference line, which is reflected already in the higher measures of $MAPE$ and MAE .

In addition, for prediction of relative density and hardness with 4 *pars* models, it is possible to evaluate the feature importance as there are multiple input process parameters. This analysis shows how significant these process parameters in predicting the desired output, which can be seen in Figure 7. It can be drawn that for the RF model, scan speed plays the most significant role in predicting the relative density, followed by layer height. Meanwhile, power and hatch distance have similar and the least importance. On the other hand, for prediction of the hardness with XGB, power has the highest influence, followed by layer height, hatch distance, and scan speed. However, it should be noted that these feature importance may not reflect the underneath physical dependency between process parameters and the measured quality [66]. Rather, they show the statistical influence of features on the model’s internal decision-making process. This, indeed, can be biased depending on the distribution of the input data distribution, and setting of the hyperparameters of the models.

It can be drawn from the above results that, despite using the same set of hyperparameters for tuning, the ML models exhibit different performance in predicting different printed properties. This observation is consistent with the “no-free lunch” theorem [49] of ML deployments since no single ML model can be universally optimal for all types of problems. This is because the input data distributions of the three properties under evaluation are different due to their nature (see Figure 4), leading to different pattern extraction for each property. In addition, only non-linear ML models can effectively capture the pattern of the input data, which aligns well with the findings in previous studies by Toprak [51] and Gor et al. [52].

Fig. 6: Model performance in terms of predicted values versus the true. From top to bottom: roughness S_a , relative density, and hardness. The discontinuous red line is the reference line where predicted values are equal to true values.

Fig. 7: Feature importance of the process parameters. From top to bottom: RF (70-30) for prediction of relative density, and XGB (80-20) for prediction of hardness.

Due to the limited input data, bootstrapping is conducted to examine how the ML models employed to assess the reliability and generality of the findings, as can be seen in Figure 11. The plots are characterized by the actual value from the experiments (purple line), the mean value of the predictions (discontinuous red line), the 95% confidence interval (green zone), and the density curve which is the smoothed version of the histogram to show the overall shape of the distribution.

In the roughness prediction, the absolute error between the predicted mean of $17.181 \mu m$ and the actual value of $17.847 \mu m$ is $0.67 \mu m$. In addition, the actual value is within the 95% confidence interval, which is a plus side. However, the confidence interval is almost $14 \mu m$ which is significantly high in comparison with the actual value of $17.847 \mu m$. This can be interpreted that if the technical requirement for the surface of a component is $15 \mu m$, then the prediction with 95% confidence will fall

between 10 μm and 24 μm . Even though this is statistically correct, the model is not sharp enough from the practical viewpoint. This partially reflects that the selected parameters are not be able to fully capture the complexity of the factors that affect the roughness. Additionally, other factors such as melt pool stability [54], and powder morphology [60] can be considered.

On the other hand, for relative density prediction, the absolute error between the predicted mean and the actual value is nearly zero. The predicted mean also falls within a relatively narrow confidence interval, from 0.989 to 0.994, meaning that the predicted error is small. From the quality control perspective, this is acceptable because it can significantly reduce the need for physical measurements. It also indicates that the selected parameters play a significant role in determining the relative density and are well-suited this task.

Last but not least, regarding hardness prediction, the predictions are highly consistent within a relatively narrow confidence interval between 502 $HV30$ and 528 $HV30$. However, the predictions collectively deviate from the actual value, which lies entirely outside the interval on the higher side. In other words, the model is overly confident in a result that is not correct. This suggests that the parameters used are not appropriate, or perhaps have little influence, on hardness, highlighting the need to explore alternative printing parameters that may be more relevant. Additional predictors could include melt pool radiation intensity data [67] or cooling rate [68], both of which directly affect microstructure formation in printed parts and subsequently the hardness level.

Overall, even though the R^2 measures for the assessed ML models in this study are above 0.4 in comparison with the baseline value in [65], and the bootstrapped predictions show reasonable initial results, there remains a significant room for improvement after addressing the quantity and quality limitation of the input data. Specifically, the number of data points can be increased, or more complementary process parameters can be included to provide a more complete picture of the underlying physics, facilitating better prediction.

Regarding quantity improvement, GAN can be employed for data augmentation to improve R^2 measure for Vickers hardness prediction as reported in [53]. This highlights the potential of using synthesis data to overcome data scarcity. Another approach is to increase the number of prints and physical measurements. Expanding the in-house data ensures its uniformity owing to the controlled experimental background (known printing setup, material, machine, etc.). However, it is inherently costly. On the other hand, curating data from published literature following [57, 58] is more time- and cost-effective. Nevertheless, the data is usually in inconsistent formats, with differences in experimental setups, and the possibility of missing critical input features. This requires careful data cleaning and feature selection. In addition, from the quality improvement perspective, to improve the prediction of surface roughness (both 2D and 3D), process-related features such as powder morphology (APS and VAR) [54], or melt pool data [60] could provide the ML models with more informative inputs. These parameters indeed influence the surface roughness and could therefore lead to more accurate predictions. Ultimately, the most effective approach is to combine both the quantity and quality improvement.

4 Conclusions and future works

Inspired by the motivation to reduce the cost for AM, especially for expensive and hard-to-machine alloys such as Ti64, a dataset was established to predict the possible desired physical properties of the printed parts. Throughout the whole study, eight different ML models were compared and discussed. The physical properties of the printed parts that were examined are 3D surface roughness, relative density, and hardness. The below conclusions can be drawn:

- For prediction of the 3D surface roughness, Π_1 and Π_2 can be used as the best predictors, with the XGB and RF models outperforming the rest.
- For prediction of the relative density, traditional predictors, i.e., VED and the four printing parameters (P, h, v, t), yielded the best results, implying that these features are more suitable for this type of structured data. The best-performing models in this case are AB and RF.
- For prediction of the hardness, only the four printing parameters proved to be effective predictors, with XGB showing the best performance among the tested models.
- In agreement with conventional ML practices, the selected models demonstrate stable and reliable performance when the training-testing ratio is between 70-30 and 80-20.
- Bootstrapping study reveals as well that the relative density can be the most reliably predicted with the current process parameters. As for the 3D surface roughness and the hardness, additional parameters of the melt pool and powder would be helpful for improving the prediction accuracy.

From the obtained results, it can be concluded that the predictive success of ML models for different material properties is highly dependent on the distribution of each target dataset. This provides a foundation for applying ML techniques in the optimization of manufacturing parameters, with the potential to significantly reduce experimental costs and accelerate process development.

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Declarations

The Authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

Data availability

Data available on reasonable request.

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Fig. 8: Model performance heatmap for roughness S_a .

Fig. 9: Model performance heatmap for relative density.

Fig. 10: Model performance heatmap for hardness.

Fig. 11: Distribution of bootstrapped predictions. From top to bottom: for roughness, relative density, and hardness.